

ARTS

WAYS OF TEACHING LISTENING IN FLT

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Abstract

This article explores the significance of listening as a critical skill in foreign language teaching (FLT). While mastery of all four language skills—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—is essential for language competence, listening holds a foundational role, especially in the context of early language acquisition. The article emphasizes that effective listening is key to developing other language skills and successful communication. Challenges in teaching and learning listening are discussed, including issues such as insufficient vocabulary, lack of concentration, and the difficulty of understanding unfamiliar accents. The article also offers practical strategies for improving listening skills, such as selecting appropriate audio materials, engaging with English films and podcasts, and focusing on correct pronunciation. The conclusion reinforces the idea that listening is a skill that can be cultivated and is essential for meaningful communication, both in language learning and in broader social contexts. The article advocates for the prioritization of listening in FLT and encourages teachers to find suitable approaches to enhance students' listening abilities.

Keywords: teaching listening, foreign language teaching, approach, method, skills, abilities

Introduction

When we say that a person speaks any language competently, it usually implies mastery of all four language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. All these skills play an extraordinary role during the learning of teaching in any language in educational institutions. The twenty first century is a period that requires language skills. Many countries are adopting trilingualism in the era of globalization. Among them is Kazakhstan. Today there are many courses and textbooks for learning other languages. Each teacher has his own methodology. As we have already mentioned, four abilities have a special place in learning any language. However, it seems that out of the four abilities, listening takes the main place. Because, when we learn our native language in early childhood, the first skill we develop is the ability to listen. We pay attention to our parents, the TV, the people around us and the world around us and repeat sounds that represent words with a certain meaning, although we are not yet aware of it. Over time, we begin to associate sounds with certain meanings, and then acquire reading and writing skills under the guidance of teachers. However, the process of learning spoken language begins with active listening and is called the language acquisition process. This process develops naturally, without much mental effort, in the sequence: listening – speaking – reading-writing. In the field of foreign language teaching (FLT), this article is devoted to a comprehensive study of learning listening skills.

Why listening is the most important skill in foreign language teaching?

In general, what is listening? Listening is the most important communication skill. Insufficient preparation for listening can be caused by insufficient preparation, time or material. In addition, teachers may not be sure if they are good listeners themselves, and therefore may be hesitant to teach this skill. Listening is receiving information from others. Listening is the first step to the development of other abilities. When we listen to others, we hear with our ears, combine pauses, letters, and sounds in our brain, and extract the information we need. According to Kazakh scientist Fauzia Orazbaeva: "understanding is the most important indicator characteristic of all types of communication activity." That is, when people talk to each other, if the other does not understand what the other is saying, there is no communication. Unfortunately, many people think that hearing and listening are the same thing. It is said that good education and intelligence are one and the same. As for the simplest example of distinguishing between the two, imagine that you are in a room with several people. Everyone is talking from different sides. You're understanding what they're saying, but you're not accepting it. After he leaves the room, all the new information will disappear from your mind. That is, hearing is a low-activity activity. And by listening we can remember information. Listening plays an important role in learning any language. That is, it will allow you to speak that language. It also depends on our native language. We are not born speaking or knowing words. We listened to the people around us, our parents, and repeated after them. Words gradually began to be stored in our brains. Later it turned out to be a sentence.

This, of course, is the result of audition. First of all, it is better for the teacher to develop listening skills in the student. Because, we can talk to others thanks to only listening.

Listening skills are important for effective communication because fifty percent or more of the time we spend communicating is spent listening. Although most students have spent a lot of time learning to read and write, less than two percent of students have received any formal listening training. Listening skills are more important than reading skills as a contributing factor to academic success. Listening in life in general or in the classroom in particular is considered one of the most commonly used skills to complete the communication process. This is not limited to a formal speech situation. It also plays an integral role in our daily lives, as the way we listen affects our attitudes, skills, and behavior.

Listening is a very difficult and active activity. It rarely develops in isolation from other skills and usually occurs in tandem with them, most often in colloquial speech.

There are many different factors under which the listener can take over and also not accept incoming speech, which can serve as an initial chain to solve the problem in listening.

Last but not least, the listener may not accurately hear what is being said due to competing background noise or ignorance of the speaker's unusual accent. Under such circumstances, the teaching understands that he listened to the speeches, but has no idea what kind of appeal was contained in this material.

Subsequently, the problem faced by a foreign listener is that speech may contain phrases in which the speaker may confuse with his native language - syntax, morphology, can also clearly understand what is being said but is unable to understand other foreign rules including semantics and pronunciation.

Previously, the most common case is when the listener perfectly understands and hears the speaker, but perhaps consciously and unconsciously "disconnected". For example, we can abruptly remember what we wanted 10 minutes ago. In such cases, our brain makes it possible to leak other information during the acceptance of incoming speech that we are not trying to process.

In many courses, when a child is taught a language, he begins not with listening, but with reading. The child makes sentences, teaches them, and memorizes grammar. You read and write great, but you don't understand. It is often forgotten that listening is the most important ability. As for the reasons for the lack of adequate hearing development:

First of all, stickiness. When you have a text in front of you, you can read it and understand it. However, when you come to the hearing, you take that sentence in a different way. The English do not read the word in parts, but in combination. When we read together, different sounds reach us as words. It seems to me that when listening, you should not translate every word. It is necessary to understand the phrase and translate it.

Secondly, lack of sufficient word stock. Without a stock of words, you may not even understand words in your native language. The lack of sufficient words has its negative impact on pronunciation.

Thirdly, we are probably all familiar with the situation when sometimes we watch a video on YouTube and do not understand it. Only after adding the subtitle "How could I not hear this word? "I know this word, it is a piece of cake," you said. The reason for this is that the reading of words in our brain is stored differently. What you hear from speakers - your brain can not count. In this case, it is better to learn to read the words correctly.

One of the most important features is the lack of listening skills. That is, when we listen, our thoughts are elsewhere or we don't pay attention. Nothing comes out of that which is not divided in real concentration. Such a thing has a negative effect not only on language learning, but even on listening in your native language.

Listening and hearing are two completely different concepts like chalk and cheese. You will probably be able to recall several situations when you missed the words of your interlocutors or audio material. This happens for various reasons, even in daily life: to forget to turn off the iron, lack of concentration during the listening test, and so forth. It is possible to overcome these difficulties only with the help of constant practice. And how to practice listening correctly and what to pay attention to in order to learn to understand spoken English?

Choose the right listening! For most students, it is not news if they do not want to listen to audio material. This is due to the fact that the audio material they have chosen is not interesting or does not suit the levels of students. By choosing the wrong audio for the levels, the student cannot understand some words, and in the worst way he does not understand the meaning of the audio and what he teaches. Therefore, it is important to choose the right audio. Properly selected audio material will be able to find an approach to this problem and it will not be so difficult to perceive English by ear. Also, by listening to it, the desire to understand and assimilate this information will naturally open. To choose the right audio format, we recommend listening to audio that is interesting for you: psychology, biography of famous people, a TV series or a movie from which you cannot tear yourself away. Everything is in your hands.

Another way to improve listening is **to watch English movies**. It is better to watch the film on the level. It is better not to just look, but to write down the words you don't understand. I think it is necessary to watch the movie in English. Because you already know the plot, the words sound a little clearer. In fact, because we are used to watching movies in Russian or English, our brain may struggle when it comes to English. I even want to watch it in Russian. In this case, the movie should continue without stopping. At first it may be strange for our brain. However, they get used to it over time.

One of the best ways to improve your listening skills is **listening to podcasts and music**. You can listen while walking on the street, while going to school

or university. It's like killing two birds with one stone. When listening, all attention should be on that audio. The best podcasts are six minute English, English with Bob and many others

Don't overlook the pronunciation

When you learn new words, make sure you also learn how they are pronounced. If you don't, it will be difficult to recognize them when you listen.

Stop watching with subtitles. Many instructors advise watching with subtitles. However, in real life, subtitles will not appear below the person who is talking to you. Moreover, once you get used to subtitles, you feel like you don't understand the movie without them. Write down all the words, phrases and sentences you heard while watching the movie.

Spanish philosopher Baltasar Gracian: "**Know or listen to those who know.**" had said. What do you need to do to listen and understand English? Of course, you should talk to someone who speaks that language. For example, as a result of getting stuck among Russians in the city and talking with them, you will not notice how you learned that language. Same with English. We take the English as a prominent representative of the English language. That is why it is better to listen to audio materials with a British accent. Today, however, the American accent is spreading widely among young people. That's why it is better to listen to both British and American.

Conclusion

Listening in language learning- it is like a water in sea: deep and fluent create harmony by filling people with comprehension and intelligence. In language learning, listening is a very important skill that is the key to understanding and communication, coordinating the teacher's guidance cues and the student's development. . Listening is the first skill that needs to be developed. Because we can communicate with

others only through listening. The parents who taught him to speak are responsible for the development of this ability, and then the teacher who infuses him with knowledge. There are many ways to teach listening. It is only necessary for the teacher to find an approach that suits the student. Listening is a skill that can be developed and improved. We show interest in others by listening. And this ability helps us to find friends and maintain close and good relations with them for a long time. The benefits of listening skills in society communication are enormous. Student with good listening skills ensure better social relationships, increase productivity, and more. To become a good listener, first determine why you have poor listening skills. After that, work on your shortcomings.

References

1. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/hearing-listening-same-thing-ian-dickson>
2. <https://www.livelaptopspec.com/is-listening-a-component-of-effective-communication/>
3. <https://bilimainasy.kz/%D1%82%D1%8B%D2%A3%D0%B4%D0%B0%D0%BB%D1%8B%D0%BC-%D0%BD%D0%B5%D0%BB%D1%96%D0%BA%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BD-%D0%BC%D0%B0%D2%A3%D1%8B%D0%B7%D0%B4%D1%8B/>
4. <https://enginorm.com/article/pochemu-reading-proshche-chem-listening>
5. <https://englishshow.ru/statii/how-to-develop-listening-skills>
6. <https://englex.ru/10-useful-advice-on-how-to-develop-listening-skills/>
7. <https://www.yurtopic.com/education/learning/listening-learn.php>